

**METHODS OF TEACHING PRESCHOOLERS A FOREIGN
LANGUAGE**

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Abstract

Every parent wants their child to grow up as an independent, diversified personality. In a world where information and social networks play the main role, it is possible and necessary to obtain new knowledge from different sources. To do this, it is useful to master the main international language - English. There are many advantages of learning this language, and we will not focus on them. Instead, let's figure out methods of teaching.

Key words: linguistic, preschool, methodology, knowledge, skills, ability, language.

The specialty "Foreign language teacher in kindergarten" can be obtained in pedagogical universities, colleges, schools - at the faculties of foreign languages and at the faculties of preschool pedagogy and psychology. It can be mastered additionally by studying a foreign language at a linguistic university and at the Institute of Foreign Languages or at advanced training courses. A small number of methods and mass manuals for preschoolers in foreign languages, primarily in English, cannot replace the textbook on the methodology of teaching a foreign language to preschoolers.

The proposed textbook contains, along with fundamental knowledge on the basics of mastering a second language at an early age, scientifically sound principles and applications of the methodology that correspond to the modern level of teaching, and also a workshop on its implementation. The main methodological developments are universal in nature and can be applied in teaching any foreign language in childhood.

The organization of early learning of a foreign language is an urgent problem modern method of teaching a foreign language at the present time. Ownership a foreign language is one of the most essential skills to achieve success in the context of global communications, therefore, at present, more and more parents begin to introduce their children to the study of foreign languages from an early age.

Therefore, it is necessary to search for effective means and techniques to increase motivation and the effectiveness of teaching a foreign language.

Early learning of foreign languages should be built, first of all, on gaming activities, which are aimed at the development and upbringing of the child, such thus socializing the child. Since the leading activity at this age is game, then the involvement of music and singing in English classes will contribute to more effective mastering by students of language, speech, sociocultural knowledge, skills and abilities and contribute to the formation of a communicative competence, that is, the ability and readiness to use a foreign language in the process of intercultural interaction in typical situations of oral and written communication.

The sooner you start learning a foreign language, the easier and more effective the process will be in the future. Modern parents have long been aware of this fact, and prefer to teach their children English almost from birth.

But how to teach a baby who cans neither read nor write, and sometimes even speak? To help the teacher - popular methods of teaching English for young learners.

#1 Glen Doman Method

Glen Doman's methodology is used by teachers for children from 6 months to middle school age. The essence of this technique is to show the student special cards with images and say aloud what is shown on them for a short period of time.

Initially, classes last no more than 10 seconds: one card - 1-2 seconds. Words, like photographs, are imprinted in the child's brain and the baby quickly memorizes a large number of words.

Of the minuses, I see that in this technique the role of the child in learning is passive - he just looks at the cards; there is no creativity here. Also, children over 3

years old are reluctant to accept training according to the Doman method, if they have not been trained in this way before.

#2 Method N. Zaitsev

The method of N. Zaitsev is intended for English lessons with children from five years old. The essence of the technique is teaching a child to read with the help of cubes with syllables. Playing with colorful cubes and checking themselves against the tables included in the set, children learn how to correctly compose English words and sentences.

A feature of Zaitsev's methodology is that there are many language exercises that help teach a child to pronounce individual letters and words correctly in any language.

The disadvantages of the methodology are the laboriousness of creating and storing materials, the lack of consistency in training.

#3 Maria Montessori Method

The motto of the methodology: "Help me do it myself." The essence of the technique is to help him learn independently and freely - for this, the child is placed in a special learning environment with didactic materials.

The teacher does not have the right to punish, encourage or teach the child; help from the teacher comes only in case of urgent need. The main focus is on the development of the intellectual abilities of the child.

In my opinion, the disadvantage of the methodology is the lack of creative elements in training. According to this methodology, creative games are not only removed from the program of work with children, but are also considered harmful and even hinder children's development.

4 Method of relying on physical actions (Total physical response - TPR)

The essence of this method is that when teaching a foreign language, it is necessary to imitate the process of mastering the native language, which is acquired in parallel with the performance of the corresponding physical actions.

The perception of new language structures is facilitated when the teacher and student accompany them with actions. The teacher plays the role of a parent: he says

words or simple phrases, such as “jump” or “look at the notebook”, and the children perform actions.

#6 Design methodology

I use the project method in classes with children from 4-5 years old. The essence of the technique is that the teacher chooses a specific topic and then devotes a series of classes to it. You offer different types of activities in the lesson, with the help of which children will learn something interesting and new about the topic of the project. And after that, you give more tasks for independent work.

#7 Learning through video

Learning through video means using only video materials for learning English. These can be films, cartoons in a foreign language, documentary videos, educational video courses.

This technique can be used to teach children of any age, as it is aimed at developing the skills of foreign speech recognition and its involuntary memorization.

There are various YouTube channels that create videos for the little ones. I use for example Nursery Rhymes, ChuchuTV, Mapleleaflearning.

#8 CLIL Method

The CLIL method (Content and Language Integrated Learning or subject-language integrated learning) is the study in English (or another foreign language) of all or several subjects - it can be the world around, drawing, geography, mathematics, literature and even physical education.

Most often, a new technique is the combined use of various elements of already known techniques. But which one is more effective and which one to choose for teaching your child? Practice and common sense will help answer these questions.

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